

Identifizieren von Unsicherheiten in historischen Rezepten

Participatory Research Workshop

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A workshop by the CHIST-ERA funded PROVIDEDH Project Partners — Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage, Austrian Academy of Sciences and University of Salamanca

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